

Inter-comparison of thermodynamic profile inversion methods based on ground-based microwave radiometers

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Introduction :

Ground-based microwave radiometers (MWRs) play a crucial role in atmospheric research by providing observations that enable the retrieval of essential thermodynamic profiles, including temperature, humidity, and Liquid Water Path (LWP). These instruments measure the brightness temperatures at multiple wavelengths, offering valuable insights into the vertical structure of the atmosphere. Various inversion methods, such as multivariate regression, neural networks, and variational approaches, have been developed to retrieve temperature and humidity profiles from MWR observations. Several scientific studies have already evaluated each of these inversion methods independently by comparison with radiosonde data, but none of them has conducted an inter-comparison of all these retrieval methods on the same dataset. In this context, the VMG aimed to establish a framework for comparing different retrieval algorithms developed to obtain temperature and humidity profiles, as well as LWP, from ground-based microwave radiometers. Within European MWR networks, and to ensure consistency between the multiple instruments deployed in specific field experiments, it is crucial to understand the effects of the processing chains used to convert raw measurements (Level 1 brightness temperatures) into geophysical parameters (Level 2 data). Indeed, various institutes in Europe and the USA, including NOAA, the University of Cologne, RPG, and Météo-France, have been contacted and have committed to participating. This collaborative project aims to promote the homogenization of MWR processing chains and advance atmospheric science research and forecasting skills, particularly at the European level. To this end, data obtained during the PANAME experiment conducted during the summers of 2022 and 2023 have been selected for this comparison.

1. PANAME dataset:

The data used in our analysis were collected during the PANAME (PARis region urbaN Atmospheric observations and models for Multidisciplinary rEsearch) experimental campaign. This multi-project initiative aims to document the spatio-temporal dynamics of the urban climate, the underlying surface mechanisms influencing thermal gradients, and the

complex interactions with the atmospheric boundary layer through intensive measurement campaigns over the Paris region during the summers of 2022 and 2023.

A comprehensive remote sensing network, as part of the PANAME initiative, has been set up to complement the surface station network. This remote sensing network includes Automatic Lidars and Ceilometers, Doppler Cloud Radars, Doppler Wind Lidars, and Microwave Radiometers. Among these instruments, our study focuses on ground-based microwave radiometers (MWRs). MWRs are passive instruments that measure the natural microwave emission in the water vapor and oxygen absorption bands from the atmosphere, providing measurements of the brightness temperatures. In particular, the MWRs used for this analysis are the Humidity and Temperature PROfiler (HATPRO) from Radiometer Physics GmbH (RPG) manufacturer. The HATPRO MWR detects radiances at 14 frequency channels (22.24, 23.04, 23.84, 25.44, 26.24, 27.84, 31.40, 51.26, 52.28, 53.86, 54.94, 56.66, 57.30, and 58.00 GHz) and on 7 elevation angles (90.0, 42.0, 30.0, 19.2, 10.2, 5.4 and 0°). Indeed, the MWR operates in two distinct spectral bands: the 22-31 GHz band is more sensitive to water vapor and cloud liquid water, whereas the 52-58 GHz band is sensitive to atmospheric temperature.

These instruments continuously provide observations of temperature and humidity profiles as well as integrated liquid and water vapor during all-sky weather conditions with high temporal resolution: every 10 minutes for temperature profiles, and every second for integrated water content and water vapor profiles.

During the PANAME campaign, three MWRs were deployed to provide temperature, humidity, and liquid water path measurements across the southwest-to-northeast transect over the Paris region from May 2022 until September 2023. The MWR that operated permanently at the SIRTA site in Palaiseau was complemented by another MWR deployed in Paris at the LISA site on the roof of a 20-meter building, and a third MWR deployed at Roissy (Charles de Gaulle) airport (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Microwave radiometer (MWR) network installed during the PANAME campaign over the Paris region at three sites: Charles de Gaulle Airport, the center of Paris (LISA site), and the SIRTA observatory. Radiosondes were deployed at the Bercy site.

This network has been reinforced by the operation of radiosondes (RS) and windsonds during intensive observation periods throughout the summers of 2022 and 2023 in the Paris

city center. In total, 116 radiosondes and 26 windsonds were launched during the two summers of 2022 and 2023. These measurements were collected to validate the different retrievals of temperature and humidity profiles obtained from ground-based microwave radiometers.

2. Retrieval methods:

Atmospheric thermodynamic profiles can be retrieved using a variety of inversion methods, such as neural networks, multivariate regression, and variational approaches.

To obtain atmospheric profiles from radiometer data, the RPG-HATPRO radiometer has its retrieval algorithm provided by the manufacturer's software. Users can select from three retrieval types: linear regression, quadratic regression, and neural networks.

We briefly present the concept of each method:

- **Linear Regression:** This method establishes a linear relationship between the brightness temperatures and the atmospheric profiles. It assumes that changes in brightness temperature linearly correspond to changes in temperature and humidity profiles.
- **Quadratic Regression:** This method uses a quadratic equation to better capture the non-linearity in the data.
- **Neural network:** is complex model that is trained on a dataset consisting of pairs of brightness temperature observations and corresponding atmospheric temperature and humidity profiles obtained from reference sources such as radiosondes or by a collection of Numerical Weather Prediction outputs. During the training phase, the neural network learns to recognize patterns and relationships between the input brightness temperature data and the desired output profiles. Through an iterative optimization process, the network adjusts its internal parameters (weights and biases) to minimize the difference between its predictions and the actual reference profiles. Once trained, the neural network can be used to perform retrievals on new brightness temperature observations.

Neural networks have been extensively applied to generate atmospheric parameters of inversion profiles. The algorithm uses standard feed forward with input, hidden, and output layers with full connection between adjacent layers. Training is conducted using a standard backpropagation algorithm, while profile determination utilizes a standard feed-forward (Cimini et al. 2006).

- **One-dimensional variational assimilation retrieval (1DVAR):**

The 1DVAR framework is based on the optimal estimation theory by Rodgers (2000). MWR observations are combined with an *a priori* estimation of the atmospheric state, which can be either a short-term forecast or a previous RS profile.

The true atmospheric vector \mathbf{x} (temperature and humidity profiles) is estimated as a combination of the observation vector \mathbf{y} (brightness temperature from the MWR) and the background state \mathbf{x}_b provided by the NWP forecast. This approach retrieves the

state of the atmosphere that is statistically most consistent with observations and background, taking into account the error characteristics of each. To this end, each source of information are weighted by corresponding uncertainty that is called the background-error-covariance matrix (B) for the background state and the observation-error-covariance matrix (R) for the observation to find the optimal state. To compute the equivalent observations from the background state (\mathbf{x}_b), a radiative transfer model is used. This model converts the atmospheric state into the observed brightness temperatures.

The goal of 1DVAR is to find the state vector \mathbf{x} that minimizes a cost function, typically represented as $J(\mathbf{x})$. The cost function consists of two terms: one measuring the difference between the background state and the retrieved state, and the other measuring the difference between the observed and simulated observations.

$$J(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_b)^T B^{-1}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_b) + \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{y} - H(\mathbf{x}))^T R^{-1}(\mathbf{y} - H(\mathbf{x}))$$

where:

H is the observation operator (radiative transfer model and interpolations from model space to observation space), “ T ” represents the transpose operator, and “ -1 ” the inverse operator.

The papers by Martinet et al. (2015, 2017) and Cimini et al. (2006) provide additional insights and practical applications of the 1DVAR framework in specific case studies.

For this study, 1-h forecasts from the operational AROME model are used as background in the 1D-Var algorithm.

3. Dataset preparation:

3.1 MWR measurements:

During the VMG, binary files containing the Level 1 radiometer data, including brightness temperatures and other relevant parameters necessary for reprocessing to Level 2 data, have been collected. These files correspond to a period of two months in June and July, obtained during the PANAME campaigns of 2022 and 2023 for the three radiometers. This Level 1 data has been sent to designated scientists for reprocessing into Level 2 data. These scientists include Tobias Marke from the University of Cologne, Dave Turner from NOAA, and Harald Czekala from RPG. An online meeting has been scheduled with these dedicated scientific experts to coordinate the inter-comparison of the different retrieval algorithms.

The first dataset of vertical profiles of temperature (T) and relative humidity (RH) was retrieved in real-time during PANAME using a multivariate regression approach (hereafter referred to as REG) provided by the manufacturer of the radiometer. These data were first evaluated through comparison with radiosonde measurements launched during the intensive observation period.

3.2 Radiosonde measurements:

Radiosondes remain one of the most accurate methods of measuring temperature and humidity profiles, and are often considered a reference standard. In this study, we used a

dataset consisting of 116 radiosondes and 26 windsonds deployed during the summers of 2022 and 2023. These measurements were collected to validate the various temperature and humidity profile retrievals obtained from ground-based microwave radiometers.

4. Statistical analysis:

The accuracy of the retrieved atmospheric profiles was quantified statistically by comparison with actual radiosonde measurements using mean bias (Bias), root-mean-square error (RMSE), and standard deviation (STD). To facilitate comparison between radiosonde observations and MWR profiles, all radiosonde profiles were interpolated vertically to match the same heights as the MWR measurements. Additionally, MWR profiles were averaged within the time window corresponding to each radiosonde launch. Data obtained in rainy or uncertain weather were excluded from the analysis. Indeed, radiometer measurements become less accurate in the presence of water film on the equipment radome during precipitation, as highlighted by Chan (2009).

4.1 REG retrieval:

In Figure 2, statistics of the differences between the retrievals from RPG and the radiosondes are plotted as boxplots in the left column. The mean bias, standard deviation, and RMSE differences between the retrieval and radiosonde profiles are reported in the right column. These results were obtained during the period from June to July 2022 at the LISA site, which is located 500 meters away from the radiosonde launch site.

For temperature retrieval, the short box length of the RPG retrieval associated with a bias (purple curve) of less than 0.7 K below 1.5 km, indicates high accuracy in retrieving temperature profiles at lower levels. However, the bias increases to -2.7 K by 2.1 km, and the RMSE exceeds 2 K (pink curve) in the upper layers. To address this issue, a bias correction method, as described in Martinet et al. (2015) and De Angelis et al. (2017), is utilized to ensure the reliability of temperature profiles above 1500 m. This method will be presented in the next section (4.2).

In the retrieved absolute humidity profiles, the absolute value of bias is less than 1 g.m^{-3} below 2 km, then decreases to 0.2 g.m^{-3} at the upper layers, with the RMSE difference being 1.2 g.m^{-3} at the surface.

Figure 2: Boxplot of retrieved profiles minus radiosondes for (a) temperature and (c) humidity. Vertical profiles of bias (bias), standard deviation (std), and root-mean-square errors (RMSE) of the MWR retrievals against radiosondes are shown in (b) and (d). MWR retrievals before bias correction are represented by magenta, cyan, and pink, whereas retrievals after bias correction are represented by grey, green, and brown for bias, standard deviation, and RMSE, respectively. Top: Temperature profiles. Bottom: Humidity profiles. The MWR data are from the MWR installed at the LISA site.

4.2 Bias correction of MWR observations using the AROME model:

In this study, the brightness temperature (TB) is calculated from AROME temperature profiles using the RTTOV model at each of the MWR channels. The mean difference between these calculated AROME TB and measured MWR forms the TB bias, which is used to correct the MWR TB data. This bias-correction method will be referred to as "BC". The retrieval after bias correction (grey line) is also compared to those before bias correction (magenta line) and is shown in Figure 2. The relative statistical behavior obtained after applying the bias correction on the raw brightness temperatures shows smaller RMSE and bias above 2 km altitude. However, a 1.5 K bias persists above the Atmospheric Boundary Layer.

An example of the comparison of the retrieved temperature before and after applying the bias correction, compared to the measured temperature from radiosonde, is shown in Figure 3. The retrieved temperature profile from the RPG product (blue line) is relatively similar to the sounding data (black line) from the ground up to a height of 1.5 km. However, the deviation increases considerably at heights above 1.5 km up to 4 km. After the bias

correction was applied, the retrieved temperature profile (magenta line) approximates the radiosonde profile, showing some improvements, but differences remain.

Figure 3: A sample comparison between the retrieved temperature from the MWR (blue curve) installed at the LISA site before bias correction, after bias correction (magenta curve), and retrieved by the 1D-Var algorithm (red curve). The black curve shows the temperature profile from a radiosonde launched at the Bercy site (at 00 UTC on 06 July 2022) around the same time as the MWR observations.

4.3 Comparison with 1DVAR retrieval:

During the summer of 2022, a one-dimensional variational (1DVAR) retrieval technique was applied to MWR observations at the LISA site. The statistical characteristics of the 1DVAR retrievals were compared to those obtained from the REG in Figure 4.

For temperature retrieval, both bias and RMSE for the 1DVAR method are smaller than those of the multivariate regression method (REG) above 1.5 km. Consequently, the retrieved profiles with 1DVAR are closer to the actual measurements (radiosonde). The improvement is notably pronounced above the first kilometer, where the instrument sensitivity begins to fade, and the influence of the background state becomes more prominent in the retrieval process. Indeed, 1DVAR initializes the iteration with a forecast state vector, which is typically more representative of the actual state. Recently, the use 1DVAR technique, has been demonstrated in numerous studies (Martinet et al., 2017, Cimini et al., 2006, 2011). However, minor degradation was observed near the ground, which is probably due to a high number of non-convergence of this method. This issue requires further investigation.

Figure 4: A comparison between the statistics of temperature (top) and humidity (bottom) profiles retrieved with (REG) multivariate regression method employed by RPG and 1DVAR, as compared to radiosondes (28 cases).

For humidity retrieval, improvements have been observed in the lower layers, particularly near the ground, where the bias decreases by around 0.3 g/m^3 , as well as the standard deviation and RMSE, which are reduced by 0.8 g/m^3 instead of 1.4 g/m^3 for REG retrieval.

4.4 Comparison of the Retrieval Between the Three MWRs:

Figure 5 highlights a comparison of the statistics of the temperature and humidity profiles of the three MWRs. It can be seen that, due to the separation between the radiometer site and the radiosonde launch site, the errors of the retrieved temperature and water vapor profiles at the SIRTA and DOA sites are larger than those obtained at the LISA site in the lower layer. This is expected, as the purpose of the PANAME campaign is to study the spatio-temporal variability of the urban climate, focusing on both urban and rural environments. In fact, the MWR at DOA and SIRTA were installed in rural and suburban environments, respectively, whereas the LISA site is an urban supersite, close to the radiosonde launch site.

In the upper layer, larger differences were found with the MWR data from SIRTA, reaching a bias of $+3\text{K}$. In contrast, the bias is significantly reduced and does not exceed 1K with the

retrievals from DOA. This can be explained by the fact that the DOA retrievals were made using reanalysis from Toulouse, whereas those from LISA and SIRTAs were reprocessed using a database of radiosonde profiles from Trappes over 10 years. This indicates that the bias above 2 km is affected not only by the inversion method but also by the data input into the database.

Figure 5: A comparison between the statistics of temperature (top) and humidity (bottom) profiles retrieved with (REG) multivariate regression method employed by RPG product of the three MWR, as compared to radiosondes.

Conclusion:

In this study, data collected during the PANAME field campaign were utilized to compare two distinct retrieval methods for determining temperature and humidity profiles from microwave radiometer measurements (brightness temperature): the multivariate regression method employed by RPG and the 1DVAR method utilizing AROME 1-hour forecasts. The achieved accuracy of the retrievals is demonstrated in terms of bias, standard deviation (std), and root-mean-square error (RMSE) with respect to simultaneous radiosonde observations.

A large bias above 1500 m (-2K) was observed with the multivariate regression method used by RPG for two MWRs installed at the SIRTAs observatory and LISA site. This discrepancy could possibly be attributed to differences in the input database used. Comparing the three MWRs using the same retrieval method (multivariate regression) showed that this bias was reduced for the CDG (DOA) site when using the database from Toulouse. A comparison should be conducted with the MWR data, testing the same database used at both MWRs installed at SIRTAs and LISA, to quantify the impact of input data.

The implementation of bias correction on the raw brightness temperatures was performed on the MWR data from the LISA site using the AROME data. This resulted in a significant reduction in temperature bias in the upper layer. However, it was not sufficient, as a 1K bias still persisted above 2km.

The Optimal Estimation method 1DVAR, which combines observations from microwave radiometers with a background (1-hour AROME forecasts) was tested in this study. This method exhibited a significant improvement in temperature profiling in the upper layer but showed slight degradation close to the ground. Additional investigation is required to address this issue.

In perspective, different retrieval algorithms, such as neural networks and 1DVAR using climatology instead of Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) data, will be compared to highlight the main drawbacks and advantages of each retrieval algorithm and to standardize the processing chains of microwave radiometer (MWR) measurements.

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